

TERRA VISION

Integrated Earth Observation Based Platform, for Novel Services
to Enhance the Mining Life Cycle of Critical Raw Materials

D7.4A

Design of the proposed super resolution architectures

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AROSICS	Automated and Robust Open-Source Image Coregistration Software
BOA	Bottom of Atmosphere
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CDS	Climate Data Store
CDSE	Copernicus Dataspace Ecosystem
CSV	Comma Separated Values
CTM	Chemical Transport Model
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DL	Deep Learning
DMS	Data Mining Sharpener
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DSen2	Deep Sentinel-2
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EEA	European Environmental Agency
EO	Earth Observation
FFTW	Fast Fourier Transform in the West
FOS	Field of View
GCP	Ground Control Points
GS	Gram-Schmidt
GSA	Gram-Schmidt Adaptive
GSD	Ground Sampling Distance
HS	Hyperspectral
JAXA	Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency
LEO	Low Earth Orbit
LST	Land Surface Temperature

MERIT	Multi-Error-Removed Improved-Terrain
ML	Machine Learning
MCD	Monte Carlo Dropout
MS	Multispectral
MSI	MultiSpectral Instrument
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
PAN	Panchromatic
PRISMA	PRecursore IperSpettrale della Missione Applicativa
Sentinel-5P	Sentinel-5 Precursor
SLSTR	Sea Land Surface Temperature Radiometer
SOTA	State of the art
SR	Super Resolution
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
TIR	Therma Infrared
TPI	Topographic Position Index
TROPOMI	Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument
UTM	Universal Transverse Mercator
WP	Work Package
VNIR	Visible Near Infrared
SWIR	Short-Wave Infrared
WGS84	World Geodetic System 1984

H1 – EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The TERRAVISION project aims to boost sustainability and efficiency in the mining industry by using advanced Earth Observation (EO) technologies. It is designing an all-encompassing platform, linking satellite, airborne, and ground-based remote sensing data to support the whole value chain of raw materials from exploration to post-closure activities. Important goals of the project include modernisation of exploration activities, improvement of risk and hazard management, optimisation of extraction rates and guaranteeing environmental compliance. The report outlines the initial design of the proposed super resolution modelling architectures for the spatial enhancement of spaceborne data. This enhancement is essential for improving the efficiency of Copernicus Sentinel and other spaceborne data products employed in mining-related applications, where precise spatial information is crucial for decision-making and operational efficiency.

H2 – GOAL/OBJECTIVES

The primary goal of this report is to present the initial design of the Machine Learning (ML)/Deep Learning (DL) Super Resolution (SR) framework that aims to enhance the spatial resolution of spaceborne data beyond the capabilities of the original imaging systems. This framework will enable the cross-platform utilisation of data from the Copernicus Sentinel missions and the PRecursores IperSpettrale della Missione Applicativa (PRISMA) satellite. It will leverage the unique characteristics of spaceborne data products by incorporating ML methods and Deep Neural Network (DNN) architectures to enhance the spatial characteristics of the observed properties, particularly in supporting mining operations. Hyperspectral pansharpening will be applied to improve the spatial resolution of PRISMA hyperspectral (HS) images from 30 meters to 5 meters. This enhancement will be accomplished by integrating the high spatial resolution panchromatic (PAN) band, which is acquired simultaneously and is included in the PRISMA datasets. The spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 multispectral (MS) images, captured by the MultiSpectral Instrument (MSI), will be enhanced to a minimum common resolution of 10 meters while maintaining the integrity of its spectral resolution. An ML-based thermal sharpening method will enhance the spatial resolution of coarse land surface temperature (LST) data products by fusing them with high spatial resolution MS data. Additionally, an ML-based multisensory data fusion technique will be implemented to estimate near surface-level concentrations of air pollutants at a higher spatial resolution of 1 km. Data from various sources will be utilised as input, including spaceborne data acquired from the Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI) onboard the Sentinel-5 Precursor (Sentinel-5P) and high-accuracy in situ data collected from ground-based air quality monitoring stations, along with meteorological, land cover, and topographic data.

H3 – METHODOLOGY

The report provides the initial design of the SR approaches developed during the first 18 months of the project. It describes the developed SR models, which will be deployed on the TerraFusion platform, ensuring the resulting solutions effectively meet the data requirements

of the TERRAVISION EO services in the mining industry. Additionally, several weaknesses in the data and the developed approaches have been identified that set the next steps in the final design of the SR architectures.

H4 – OUTCOMES/CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable, part of the Horizon Europe project TERRAVISION, focuses on describing the initial design of the SR approaches to enhance the spatial resolution of spaceborne EO data and meet the data requirements for mining-related applications.

In more detail, this report describes the initial design of the SR methods for enhancing the spatial resolution of:

- PRISMA HS data, which are paired with high spatial resolution PAN images.
- Sentinel-2 MSI data to a common spatial resolution of at least 10 m.
- LST data acquired from various spaceborne platforms by exploiting the spatial details available in high spatial resolution multispectral data.
- Sentinel-5P data and simultaneously estimating the near-surface-level concentrations of various air pollutants.

Key outcomes/conclusions in bullet points

- The **Sentinel-2 DL-based SR** model aims to enhance the spatial resolution of all bands to a uniform finer resolution of **10 meters**. Alongside the improved Sentinel-2 images, **uncertainty metrics** are provided to help assess the confidence in the SR models predictions.
- **HS pansharpening** for enhancing the spatial resolution of **PRISMA** data to **5 meters**. The pansharpening method can also be applied to MS images if a PAN image is available.
- **Thermal sharpening technique** to enhance the spatial resolution of **Sentinel-3 SLSTR from 1 km to 10 m** through fusion with high spatial resolution Sentinel-2 multispectral data.
- **Multisensory data fusion** for estimating **1 km near-surface-level** air pollutant concentrations from **Sentinel-5P data**.

1. Introduction

As described in WP7, the main objective of T7.2 is to establish an ML/DL framework and algorithms designed to enhance the spatial resolution of MS and HS spaceborne data beyond the capabilities of the original imaging systems. This framework will enable cross-platform utilisation of the Sentinel and PRISMA satellites, leveraging the inherent characteristics of spaceborne data and applying SR modelling techniques, including DNN architectures. The aim is to improve the spatial characteristics of the observed properties to support mining operations. Specifically, we aim to increase the spatial resolution of the Sentinel-2 coarser bands from 20 m and 60 m to 10 m, while preserving the integrity of the spectral resolution. Additionally, a pansharpening technique will be applied to PRISMA hyperspectral images to enhance their spatial resolution using high spatial resolution panchromatic images. ML-based methods will be applied to Sentinel-3 SLSTR and Sentinel-5P data to enhance the estimation of land surface temperature (LST) and near-surface-level concentrations of air pollutants.

Based on the above-mentioned goals and objectives, as well as the SOTA report in D7.3, four different SR tools have been developed to enhance the spatial resolution of spaceborne data and support their application in mining-related services. The first component involves the pansharpening of PRISMA HS images to enhance the spatial resolution from 30 m to 5 m. This enhancement can be accomplished by integrating the high spatial resolution PAN band, which is acquired simultaneously and is included in the PRISMA datasets. The second component involves a DL-based SR model that enhances the spatial resolution of Sentinel-2's coarse bands to match that of its finer bands (i.e., 10 m). The third component focuses on sharpening thermal data, such as Sentinel-3 SLSTR, by fusing it with higher spatial resolution Sentinel-2 MS data. The final step involves downscaling Sentinel-5P data to estimate near-surface concentrations of air pollutants at a higher spatial resolution of 1 km by combining them with data from various sources, including meteorological data and land cover maps.

This document describes the initial design and development of the four individual SR components. A detailed description of each component is provided to facilitate the interpretation of the design.

1.1 Deliverable Description

Initial design of super resolution modelling architectures.

1.2 Purpose of the Deliverable

This document aims to present the initial design of spaceborne data SR methods and ensure alignment with operational needs. This can be achieved by developing the most effective approaches identified in the previous SOTA report. Moreover, the strengths and limitations of the developed SR methods are identified and will be addressed throughout the project.

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as scheduled.

1.3 Intended Audience

The dissemination level of this report is Public. It is specifically intended for all partners, especially the leaders of tasks related to WP7-8 Analysis Ready Data and Raw Spectral Signatures, WP9-10 EO Services for the Mining Industry, and the WP11 Green & Resilience Accountability component. This deliverable ensures that the participants are informed about the spatial resolution enhancement methods planned for development and deployment on the TerraFusion platform, which can serve as input data to enhance their services.

1.4 Deliverable structure and relation with other work packages/deliverables

The sections following the introduction are a detailed review of the SR approaches, which have been developed:

1. Hyperspectral Pansharpening (Section 2)
2. Sentinel-2 SR (Section 3)
3. Thermal Sharpening (Section 4)
4. Multisensory Data Fusion of Sentinel-5P (Section 0)

The deliverable is interconnected with several work packages in the TERRAVISION project. It is a crucial component of WP7-8, focused on Analysis Ready Data and Raw Spectral Signatures, which aims to showcase a novel framework that integrates advanced image and feature modelling approaches with ML and DL techniques, to support the complete cycle of critical raw and secondary materials.

Moreover, the spatially refined outputs produced through super-resolution and pansharpening directly benefit the objectives of WP9 and WP10, which are centered on EO Services tailored for the Mining Industry. The improved image detail allows for more reliable detection of geological patterns, infrastructure, and environmental changes, thereby enhancing decision-support tools and operational efficiency.

Finally, this work also aligns with the goals of WP11, which addresses the Green & Resilience Accountability Component. By feeding higher-quality spaceborne data into sustainability and resilience metrics, the project is better equipped to evaluate environmental impact, ensure regulatory compliance, and promote responsible mining practices.

Through these cross-cutting contributions, the deliverable serves as a critical enabler for multiple components of the TERRAVISION platform, reinforcing its integrated and innovation-driven approach to EO-based solutions in the mining sector.

2. Hyperspectral Pansharpening

2.1 Introduction

HS imaging, which captures information across hundreds of contiguous spectral bands, has become invaluable in applications such as mineral exploration and geological mapping. Despite offering rich spectral detail, HS sensors often suffer from limited spatial resolution due to constraints in available incident energy and sensor design. Conversely, PAN sensors provide high spatial resolution but capture only a single spectral band. This trade-off limits the effectiveness of HS images in many remote sensing applications that require both high spatial and spectral fidelity.

To address this challenge, the PRISMA mission was designed to simultaneously capture HS images at 30 m spatial resolution and PAN images at 5 m resolution. These complementary datasets can be fused through pansharpening techniques to produce high-resolution HS images with a spatial resolution of 5 m. This fusion capability serves as a foundational component for enhancing the utility of PRISMA data in practical applications. A dedicated pansharpening service will process the 239 spectral bands acquired by the PRISMA HS sensor to generate spatially enhanced images over the TERRAVISION mining sites.

Pansharpening aims to merge the spatial detail of the PAN image with the spectral richness of the HS data to create a high-resolution HS data cube. This task is complex due to the high dimensionality of HS data, the need to maintain spectral consistency across all bands, and the challenge of accurately modelling the sensor's spectral response functions. Moreover, algorithms must be robust to nonlinear mixing effects and avoid introducing spatial or spectral artefacts that could distort scientific interpretation.

Building on the prior deliverable (D7.3), which evaluated a wide range of SOTA pansharpening methods, the best algorithm was selected for implementation based on theoretical robustness, practical feasibility, and demonstrated performance with spaceborne hyperspectral and multispectral datasets. While multispectral pansharpening is also an important element of the broader SR framework, the proposed algorithm will be tested in a later phase of the project once relevant MS data from the contributing missions become available.

This section outlines the initial design of a pansharpening pipeline tailored to PRISMA data. More specifically, the following sections present the hyperspectral pansharpening framework, detailing the necessary data preprocessing and the pansharpening method. Together, these components provide a comprehensive overview of the system's design and its anticipated performance in real-world processing conditions.

2.2 PRISMA Mission and Products

The PRISMA payload integrates two core imaging systems: a PAN camera and an HS imager. The PAN camera captures high-resolution imagery within the visible spectrum (400–700 nm),

while the HS imager acquires data across a broader spectral range (400–2500 nm) with fine spectral resolution (Table 1).

Each PRISMA scene covers an area of approximately 30 km × 30 km and includes both a PAN image and a coregistered HS data cube. The hyperspectral data is divided into two sub-cubes:

- VNIR (Visible and Near-Infrared): 66 bands, spanning 400–1000 nm
- SWIR (Shortwave Infrared): 173 bands, spanning 1000–2500 nm

Together, they provide 239 contiguous spectral bands, with a spectral sampling interval of less than 12 nm.

The HS imager uses a push-broom configuration to collect 1000 pixels across the 30 km swath, achieving a ground sampling distance (GSD) of 30 meters and a field of view (FOV) of 2.77°. The PAN sensor, operating solely in the 400–700 nm range, captures 6000 pixels across the same swath at a finer GSD of 5 meters. PRISMA operates in a Sun-synchronous low-Earth orbit (LEO) with a nominal 29-day repeat cycle. Off-nadir imaging capabilities enable target-specific revisits in under 7 days.

Data products are available at three processing levels. The Terravision HS Pansharpener service will utilise Level-2D products, which provide bottom-of-atmosphere (BOA) reflectance data corrected for atmospheric effects. All data are geocoded and delivered in HDF5 format.

	HS-VNIR	HS-SWIR	PAN
Swath (km)	30	30	30
Spatial resolution (m)	30	30	5
Spatial pixels	1000	1000	6000
Spectral range (nm)	400-1010	920-2500	400-700
Spectral bands	66	173	1
Spectral Sampling Interval, SSI (nm)	7.1-11	6.5-11	-
Spectral Resolution (nm)	9-13	9-14.5	-
Absolute Radiometric Accuracy	≤ 5% (Stability ≤ ± 1%)	≤ 5% (Stability ≤ ± 1%)	-
MTF@Nyquist Frequency	VNIR/SWIR along track > 0.18 VNIR/SWIR across track > 0.34		PAN along track > 0.1 PAN across track > 0.2

Table 1. Main PRISMA product's technical features

2.3 Data Preprocessing

PRISMA Level-2D products with BOA reflectance will be the input of the Terravision HS pansharpener service. These reflectances are derived from a MODTRAN-based atmospheric correction of the at-sensor radiance (processor version 02.05). The product is ortho-projected

and geocoded in UTM projection without the use of external ground control points (GCPs). Four cloud-free PRISMA Level-2D images captured over the Terravision mining sites were acquired from the ASI PRISMA portal¹ through on-demand request and were used for testing (Table 2).

Mining Sites	HS-VNIR
Canteras	PRISMA: PRS_L2D_STD_20220712110958_20220712111002_0001
La Zarza	PRISMA: PRS_L2D_STD_20221008112624_20221008112628_0001
San Telmo	PRISMA: PRS_L2D_STD_20230927112942_20230927112947_001
Tharsis	PRISMA: PRS_L2D_STD_20200224112618_20200224112623_0001
TernaMag	PRISMA: Not available

Table 2. PRISMA acquisitions over TERRAVISION mining sites

The PRISMA images can be read using GDAL and the h5py Python library to remove atmospheric water absorption bands, low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) bands, and bands affected by severe stripping, which is caused by a temporary unbalanced response of a VNIR or SWIR detector. More specifically, the preliminary band removal consists of three steps: a) automatic elimination of “zero bands”, i.e. defective bands flagged as zero in metadata and/or bands with zero-valued pixels > 90% out of the total, b) exclusion of spectral bands corresponding to water vapour absorption windows between 1350-1470 nm, 1800-1950 nm and as stated by (Alicandro et al., 2022) at around 920, 1120 and 2020 nm, and exclusion of bands poorly correlated to neighbouring ones (e.g. “salt-and-pepper”, “Gaussian like” noise), including the first 3 bands (406.9-423.8 nm) of VNIR and the last 23 bands of SWIR (2342.8-2477.1 nm) which were also filtered out. It is essential to note that all data cubes are stored in L2D products as Digital Numbers (i.e., unsigned integers). Therefore, the following rescaling formula must be applied to convert the digital numbers to reflectance units:

$$XXX = L2ScaleXXXMin + XXX_{DN} \cdot \frac{L2ScaleXXXMax - L2ScaleXXXMin}{65535 \text{ (i.e., } 2^{16} - 1)} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

where $L2ScaleXXXMin$ and $L2ScaleXXXMax$ are the minimum and maximum scaling factor values, which are specified inside the image file and the XXX_{DN} is the PRISMA image digital number. Afterwards, the VNIR and SWIR bands are assembled into a single datacube spanning the VNIR and SWIR wavelength range. The final number of bands varies among the four datasets.

Finally, each PRISMA datacube can be coregistered with a Sentinel-2 image acquired close to the acquisition time of PRISMA to correct the geometrical displacements of PRISMA data, achieving a geolocation accuracy of up to 200 m. The co-registration is performed with AROSICS (Scheffler et al., 2017), which applies an improved phase-correlation approach (Feroosh et al., 2002), employing discrete Fourier transformation domain (Fastest Fourier

¹ <https://prisma.asi.it>

Transform in the West, FFTW) (Bracewell and Kahn, 1996; Frigo and Johnson, 2005, 1997) to derive pixel geometrical displacement among a pre-constructed grid of tie points. The detailed description of the algorithm is available in (Scheffler et al., 2017). This operation can be performed by interpolating the HS bands at the 5 m panchromatic scale using bicubic interpolation and by utilising the Sentinel-2 temporally closest acquisition as a reference. Sentinel-2 band 4 at 665 nm is used as a common reference for displacement estimation of the 664 nm PRISMA band and the PAN band. It should be noted that the estimated displacement between the 664 nm band of PRISMA and the Sentinel-2 B4 band is finally used for all VNIR and SWIR bands of PRISMA, which are perfectly coregistered in the original ASI product.

After these processing steps, the PRISMA data are ready for pansharpening.

2.4 Pansharpening Method

This section describes the HS pansharpening technique selected for development and testing.

2.4.1 Gram-Schmidt Adaptive

Gram-Schmidt Adaptive (GSA) is an advanced pansharpening technique used to enhance the spatial resolution of MS or HS images using a high-resolution PAN band. Based on the classic Gram-Schmidt (GS) pansharpening method, the adaptive variant improves both spatial sharpness and spectral fidelity.

The standard GS method follows a component substitution approach and consists of the following steps:

1. A lower spatial resolution PAN image is simulated.
2. The Gram-Schmidt transformation is applied to the simulated lower spatial resolution PAN image and the corresponding lower spatial resolution HS image bands. The simulated lower spatial resolution PAN image is employed as the first band in the Gram-Schmidt transformation.
3. The statistics of the higher spatial resolution PAN image are adjusted to match the statistics of the first transform band resulting from the Gram-Schmidt transformation to produce a modified higher spatial resolution PAN image.
4. The modified higher spatial resolution PAN image is substituted for the first transform band, resulting from the Gram-Schmidt transformation, to produce a new set of transformed bands.
5. The inverse Gram-Schmidt transformation is applied to the new set of transform bands to produce the enhanced spatial resolution HS image.

The GSA method introduces a preprocessing step to address spectral distortion and maintain higher sharpness during the simulation of the low spatial resolution version of the PAN images used in the forward GS transformation. This process involves generating synthetic PAN in a manner that considers the sensor's spectral response by weighting the contributions from different spectral channels differently. The preprocessing steps to be performed before the standard GS spectral sharpening are the following:

1. Reduce the original full-resolution PAN image to the size of the MS/HS images by low-pass filtering and decimation. Let us denote this image as P_{\downarrow} .
2. Assume a model according to which, at every pixel position it holds that:

$$P_{\downarrow} = w_1 \cdot HS_1 + w_2 \cdot HS_2 + w_3 \cdot HS_3 + \dots + w_n \cdot HS_n + \varepsilon \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

where w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n are scalar constants.

3. Find $\hat{w}_1, \hat{w}_2, \dots, \hat{w}_n$ and $\hat{\varepsilon}$ that determine an estimate \hat{P}_{\downarrow} of P_{\downarrow} such that the mean square value of the residue $\|P_{\downarrow} - \hat{P}_{\downarrow}\|$ is minimized.
4. Take \hat{P}_{\downarrow} as the simulated PAN image to be given as input to the GS procedure.

2.5 Pansharpener Service

The GSA pansharpener algorithm is implemented in Python and is designed to process preprocessed PRISMA HS and PAN image pairs. Before pansharpener, the input datasets undergo band selection to remove low-quality spectral bands and are geometrically coregistered to ensure spatial alignment. All PRISMA images acquired over the Terravision demonstrators have been acquired, and new acquisitions during the project have been requested. The acquired PRISMA images will be stored on the TerraFusion platform, and will be the input of the HS Pansharpener service. The output of the service consists of PRISMA HS images sharpened to a spatial resolution of 5 meters. These enhanced images are exported in GeoTIFF format for further analysis. Figures 2 through 5 illustrate the original PRISMA HS and PAN image pairs alongside the resulting pansharpener hyperspectral images for four TERRAVISION mining sites.

New pansharpener PRISMA images will be available to users upon request, as these images can only be obtained through on-demand requests from the ASI PRISMA portal. Additionally, both the initial and pansharpener PRISMA images will be accessible only to consortium members and users of the TerraFusion platform due to data license restrictions.

Figure 1. Functional view of the TERRAVISION HS Pansharpener Service

Panchromatic

Hyperspectral (RGB) [663, 560, 466 nm]

Pansharpened (RGB) [663, 560, 466 nm]

Figure 2 Left: A true color composite of the original PRISMA hyperspectral (HS) image, captured over the San Telmo mine on September 27, 2023, with a resolution of 30 meters. Center: the PRISMA panchromatic (PAN) image, which has a resolution

of 5 meters. Right: true color composite of the PRISMA HS image, enhanced to a spatial resolution of 5 meters using the GSA pansharpener method.

Panchromatic

Hyperspectral (RGB) [663, 560, 466 nm]

Pansharpened (RGB) [663, 560, 466 nm]

Figure 3 Left: A true color composite of the original PRISMA hyperspectral (HS) image, captured over the La Zarza mine on October 8, 2022, with a resolution of 30 meters. Center: the PRISMA panchromatic (PAN) image, which has a resolution of 5

meters. Right: true color composite of the PRISMA HS image, enhanced to a spatial resolution of 5 meters using the GSA pansharpener method.

Panchromatic

Hyperspectral (RGB) [663, 560, 466 nm]

Pansharpener (RGB) [663, 560, 466 nm]

Figure 4 Left: A true color composite of the original PRISMA hyperspectral (HS) image, captured over the Canteras mine on July 12, 2022, with a resolution of 30 meters. Center: the PRISMA panchromatic (PAN) image, which has a resolution of 5 meters. Right: true color composite of the PRISMA HS image, enhanced to a spatial resolution of 5 meters using the GSA pansharpener method.

Panchromatic

Hyperspectral (RGB) [663, 560, 466 nm]

Pansharpened (RGB) [663, 560, 466 nm]

Figure 5 Left: A true color composite of the original PRISMA hyperspectral (HS) image, captured over the Tharsis mine on February 24, 2020, with a resolution of 30 meters. Center: the PRISMA panchromatic (PAN) image, which has a resolution of 5 meters. Right: true color composite of the PRISMA HS image, enhanced to a spatial resolution of 5 meters using the GSA pansharpening method.

2.6 Future Steps

GSA is a complex and computationally demanding process that requires forward and backward transformations of the entire image. To tackle this issue, we will implement the solution proposed by (Maurer, 2013) to compute the transform coefficients directly and in advance.

3. Sentinel-2 Super-Resolution

3.1 Introduction

Sentinel-2 is a valuable tool for various mining-related applications, such as exploration, environmental management, and site rehabilitation. Its high-resolution imagery, frequent revisits, and broad spectral range provide essential data that support various aspects of mining operations and their environmental impacts. The Sentinel-2 satellite system comprises twin satellites equipped with an optical payload that includes sensors for visible, near-infrared, and shortwave-infrared wavelengths. This payload incorporates 13 spectral bands: 4 bands at 10 m resolution, 6 bands at 20 m resolution, and 3 bands at 60 m resolution. The decision to capture images at different spatial resolutions is driven by several factors, including limitations in storage and transmission bandwidth, improved signal-to-noise ratios in certain bands due to larger pixel sizes, and specific bands designed for particular purposes that do not require high spatial resolution, such as atmospheric correction. However, spatial data analysis benefits from having all available data share a common and optimal spatial resolution, allowing for the extraction of more detailed and accurate information. To this end, the initial component of the Sentinel-2 SR service aims to enhance the spatial resolution of the coarser bands (20 m and 60 m) to match the resolution of the finer bands (10 m).

This section outlines the initial design of a globally applicable SR model that can be used to enhance the spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 Level-2A products for any Sentinel-2 scene, especially those captured over the areas of interest.

3.2 Sentinel-2 Data

Sentinel-2 satellites carry on-board MSI, which offers wide-swath multispectral imagery with 13 spectral bands spanning the visible, NIR and shortwave infrared regions (Table 3). Various Sentinel-2 data products are available through Copernicus Dataspace Ecosystem (CDSE) ranging from geometrically corrected top of atmosphere reflectance products (Level-1C) to bottom of atmosphere (Level-2A). The Sentinel-2 SR service will use as input the Sentinel-2 Level-2A product. The Level-2A product provides orthorectified surface reflectance with subpixel multispectral and multitemporal registration accuracy.

Spectral Band	Band Description	Central Wavelength (nm)	Spatial Resolution (m)
B1	Coastal aerosol	433-453	60
B2	Blue	458-523	10
B3	Green	543-578	10
B4	Red	650-680	10
B5	Red-edge 1	698-713	20
B6	Red-edge 2	733-748	20

B7	Red-edge	773-793	20
B8	Near infrared (NIR)	785-900	10
B8A	Near infrared narrow (NIRn)	855-875	20
B9	Water vapour	935-955	60
B10	Shortwave infrared / Cirrus	1360-1390	60
B11	Shortwave infrared 1 (SWIR1)	1565-1655	20
B12	Shortwave infrared 2 (SWIR2)	2100-2280	20

Table 3. The Sentinel-2 spectral bands

3.3 Sentinel-2 SR Methodology

The Sentinel-2 SR service is an implementation of the Deep Sentinel-2 (DSen2) method (Lanaras et al., 2018), a supervised DL-based SR approach. The DSen2 model is enhanced by using the Monte Carlo Dropout (MCD) method for uncertainty estimation, which allows for assessing the confidence in the model's predictions. Next, a description of the DSen2 architecture, the uncertainty estimation method, the development of the training dataset, and the model training process follows.

3.3.1 DSen2 Architecture

The DSen2 (Lanaras et al., 2018) is a CNN model for super-resolving the low spatial resolution Sentinel-2 bands (i.e., 20m and 60m) to 10 m spatial resolution. The network follows a ResNet architecture, as shown in Figure 6, and must be trained for two different scale factors (i.e., 2x and 6x). For 2x, the input is 10 and 20 m and for 6x the input is 10, 20 and 60 m. The output for 2x is 6 SR bands (20 m) and for 6x 2 SR bands (60 m).

Figure 6 DSen2 Super-Resolution Neural network architecture as defined by (Lanaras et al., 2018)

3.3.2 Uncertainty Estimation

In this project, we utilise a well-known technique for estimating uncertainty called MCD (Gal & Ghahramani, 2015). MCD is a framework that trains approximate Bayesian Neural Networks by modifying the behaviour of the regularisation technique known as dropout. During the training phase, dropout randomly zeros out certain activations in specific feature maps with a certain probability. The main idea behind MCD is to keep this behaviour active during inference, allowing us to obtain a stochastic output.

We can generate samples from the posterior predictive distribution by performing M stochastic forward passes through the model, each with different randomly sampled dropout masks. The standard deviation of these predictions can be calculated as an estimate of uncertainty. One of the key advantages of MCD is its ease of implementation; if the deterministic model already includes dropout layers, no modifications to the underlying architecture or training process are necessary. In our case, dropout layers were added after each convolution layer.

In the context of SR given M predictions, we aggregate them to create a mean output image, which serves as the super-resolution image. Additionally, we compute the per-pixel standard deviation, which indicates the level of uncertainty associated with the predictions.

3.3.3 Training Dataset

A large training dataset of Sentinel-2 data was deemed essential for training a network capable of super-resolving random Sentinel-2 images. We collected atmospherically corrected Sentinel-2 Level-2A tiles from 45 randomly selected locations, sourced from the CDSE. This selection was made to ensure a wide global distribution and to cover a variety of climate zones and land cover types. Additionally, we gathered a separate dataset of 5 Sentinel-2 Level-2A tiles from potential areas of interest for the Terravision mining sites, which were utilised for testing purposes. To facilitate the training and testing processes, we focused solely on images with low cloud cover and no undefined (“no data”) pixels. The locations of the training and test images are depicted in Figure 7. Of the images in this training dataset, 80% are allocated for training, while the remaining 20% are designated as the validation set.

Figure 7 Locations of Sentinel-2 tiles selected for training and testing

The employed SR model is fully supervised and requires a significant amount of training data, including low-resolution input images and their corresponding high-resolution outputs. A primary challenge in SR tasks is constructing the training, validation, and testing datasets. This is particularly difficult because ground truth images with a resolution of 10 meters are not available for the 20-meter and 60-meter bands.

In the absence of high-resolution reference images, the method involves degrading the images to the desired scale factor to serve as input data, while the original observed images are used as reference outputs. This approach is the most commonly used method for creating datasets in DL-based Sentinel-2 SR applications. It is grounded in Wald's protocol, which assumes that the spectral correlation of an image remains self-similar over a limited range of scales.

In practice, to generate training data with the desired scale ratio of 2 and 6, we downsampled the original Sentinel-2 data by first blurring them with a Gaussian filter of standard deviation $\sigma = 1/s$ pixels. Then, we downsampled by averaging over $s \times s$ *pixel* kernel size, with $s = 2$ and $s = 6$, respectively. In this way, we obtained two datasets for training, validation and testing. The first dataset consists of fine resolution images at 20 m and coarse resolution images of 40 m, created by downsampling the original 10 m and 20 m bands by a factor of 2. It served to train the CNN model for 2x SR. The second one consists of images with 60 m, 120 m and 360 m spatial resolution, downsampled from the original 10 m, 20 m and 60 m data. This dataset was used to learn a network for 6x SR.

To ensure that the network's training was computationally manageable, each input image was divided into numerous small patches of appropriate size. Each image was split into 1,000 random patches. For the 2x super-resolution model, the patch size is 32 x 32 pixels, while for the 6x super-resolution model, it is 96 x 96 pixels.

The processing of the dataset was carried out in Python. The Gaussian blurring was executed using the gaussian filter from the multidimensional image processing package, `scipy.ndimage`. The downscaling was accomplished with the `skimage.measure.block_reduce` function. Finally, the upscaling of the coarse image patches to fit the dimensions of the fine image patches was implemented using the default order of 1. Lastly, the tiling into patches was completed with the `gdal.Translate` function.

3.3.4. Training Setup

The network was developed and trained with Pytorch on batches of 64 tiles with mean absolute error as the loss function and the ADAM with Nesterov momentum as an optimizer. The learning rate was 10^{-4} , which was reduced by a factor of 2 when stable for 5 epochs. The model was trained for 150 epoches with early stopping.

3.4 Sentinel-2 SR Service

The two trained neural networks, designed for downscaling 20 m and 60 m bands to 10 m resolution, form the basis of the Sentinel-2 SR tool, which is implemented using Python and PyTorch. The tool can super-resolve entire Sentinel-2 Level 2A images as delivered by CDSE.

The under-processed image is read partially with the GDAL library to reduce the memory requirements. Each accessed section of the Sentinel-2 image, including both the 20 m and 60 m bands, is first resampled to a 10 m grid using the bilinear interpolation algorithm. This resampled data is then fed into the trained DSen2 model, which adds the 10 m spatial resolution details. The resulting information is saved in an output GeotIFF file. This file is named after the original Sentinel-2 filename, prefixed with "SR_". The final super-resolved image includes 12 bands with 10 m spatial resolution. The super-resolved images will be stored in the Terrafusion platform. An additional supplementary image will be available for each super-resolved image, which will contain the uncertainty values for the super-resolved 20 m and 60 m bands. Next, super-resolved Sentinel-2 images and their accompanying uncertainty metrics acquired over the five different mining sites are presented as proof of concept. Super-resolved Sentinel-2 images will be available to users upon request.

Figure 8. Functional view of the TERRAVISION Sentinel-2 SR Service

Figure 9 Top: (a) Input Sentinel 2 bands at 10 m (RGB Bands 4,3,2), (b) 20 m (RGB Bands 5,6,7) and (c) 60 m (RGB Bands 1,9) spatial resolution, Middle: Super-resolved bands at 10 m spatial resolution (d) (RGB Bands 5,6,7) and (e) (RGB Bands 1,9), Bottom: MCD uncertainty for Bands 5 and 9. (Location: Tharsis Mine)

Figure 10. Top: (a) Input Sentinel 2 bands at 10 m (RGB Bands 4,3,2), (b) 20 m (RGB Bands 5,6,7) and (c) 60 m (RGB Bands 1,9) spatial resolution, Middle: Super-resolved bands at 10 m spatial resolution (d) (RGB Bands 5,6,7) and (e) (RGB Bands 1,9), Bottom: MCD uncertainty for Bands 5 and 9. (Location: TernaMag Mine)

Figure 11 Top: (a) Input Sentinel 2 bands at 10 m (RGB Bands 4,3,2), (b) 20 m (RGB Bands 5,6,7) and (c) 60 m (RGB Bands 1,9) spatial resolution, Middle: Super-resolved bands at 10 m spatial resolution (d) (RGB Bands 5,6,7) and (e) (RGB Bands 1,9), Bottom: MCD uncertainty for Bands 5 and 9. (Location: Canteras Mine)

3.5 Future Steps

The release of the SEN2VEN μ S dataset (Michel et al., 2022), which provides same-day, cloud-free surface reflectance patches from Sentinel-2 and VEN μ S at 10 m, 20 m, and 5 m resolutions, respectively, opens up new possibilities for enhancing further the spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 images. Future work will focus on utilising this dataset to enhance all Sentinel-2 bands to a uniform 5-meter resolution, leveraging the high-quality VEN μ S imagery as reference.

4. Thermal Sharpening

4.1 Introduction

Thermal infrared (TIR) remote sensing is a valuable approach for estimating land surface temperature, offering critical insights for a range of mining-related applications. TIR imagery supports exploration, safety monitoring, and environmental management by revealing temperature anomalies linked to specific minerals or geological features. It also enables the monitoring of mine slope stability and tailings dams by detecting thermal patterns that may signal potential failure zones or water seepage. Furthermore, TIR data play an important role in assessing land reclamation efforts by tracking soil temperature and moisture content—key indicators of vegetation health and soil recovery. Currently, the Sentinel satellite constellation includes only a single thermal sensor aboard Sentinel-3, with a coarse spatial resolution of 1 km. This resolution is inadequate for the spatial detail required in mining contexts. Consequently, there is a clear need for an effective thermal sharpening technique to improve the spatial resolution of Sentinel-3 thermal data, making it more suitable for mining and related applications.

This section outlines the initial design of an ML-based thermal sharpening approach that can be used to enhance the spatial resolution of Sentinel-3 SLSTR thermal data by fusing them with high spatial resolution Sentinel-2 multispectral data.

4.2 Sentinel-3 SLSTR Thermal Data

SLSTR is a dual-scan temperature radiometer operating for the Sentinel-3 mission. The SLSTR Level 2 Land Product has a spatial resolution of 1 km and provides land surface temperature (LST) estimates, as well as associated parameters, such as LST uncertainty, normalised difference vegetation index (NDVI), vegetation type, atmospheric column water vapour content, and parameters related to LST retrieval. The thermal sharpening service component will use as input the Sentinel-3 SLSTR LST product, which is delivered in NetCDF format through CDSE.

4.3 Thermal Sharpening

The thermal sharpening method implemented is based on the Data Mining Sharpener (DMS) approach proposed by (Gao et al., 2006). This method utilises high-resolution Sentinel-2 MS data as independent features, which are aggregated to match the native 1 km spatial resolution of Sentinel-3 SLSTR data. Only homogeneous Sentinel-2 pixels, identified by calculating the sub-pixel variation during aggregation, along with the corresponding Sentinel-3 temperature values, are used as samples to learn the relationship between temperature and reflectance values. This is achieved through an ensemble decision tree regression method, which is performed both locally (i.e., within a sliding window) and globally (i.e., across the entire image). The results are combined by analysing the residuals calculated between the regression outputs and the low-resolution thermal data. Finally, residual analysis and bias correction are conducted to ensure that the sharpened high-resolution pixels are consistent

with their corresponding low-resolution temperature pixels. Figure 12 illustrates the implemented processing workflow.

Figure 12 Sentinel-3 SLSTR & Sentinel-2 thermal sharpening workflow

4.4 Thermal Sharpening Service

The thermal sharpening service takes as an input a Sentinel-3 SLSTR Level 2 LST image and a fine resolution Sentinel-2 Level-2A image. The images must be overlapping and acquired temporally close to each other. The Sentinel-2 data is first super-resolved to achieve a finer spatial resolution of 10 meters across all its spectral bands, using the Sentinel-2 SR tool described in Section 2. The input data from Sentinel-3's SLSTR sensor is reprojected to match the projection system of the Sentinel-2 data using the GDAL Python library. Only the spatially overlapping areas of both images are utilised for the subsequent processing. For the ensemble decision tree regression, the scikit-learn library is employed. In this method, each decision tree uses a random subset of the training samples, drawn with replacement, a technique known as Bagging. The final regression output is the average of the values produced by the ensemble of decision trees. The developed thermal sharpening tool was applied to Sentinel 3 and Sentinel 2 image pairs acquired over the Terravision AOIs. Figures 14-16 present subsets of the Sentinel 2 and Sentinel 3 image pairs and the resulting thermal-sharpened images from the thermal-sharpening tool.

At the current stage of the project, thermal sharpened Sentinel-3 SLSTR temperature data will be available upon request. The Sentinel images will be acquired from CDSE, and the thermal sharpened outputs of GeoTIFF format will be stored on the TerraFusion Platform (Figure 13).

Figure 13 Functional view of the TERRAVISION Thermal sharpening Service

Sentinel-2 RGB [432] 10m

Sentinel-3 SLSTR 1km

Sentinel-3 SLSTR 10m

 NoData

Figure 14 Left: Sentinel-2 image acquired over Tharsis mine, Center: Sentinel-3 SLSTR LST image at its native spatial resolution of 1 km, Right: Thermal sharpened Sentinel-3 SLSTR LST data at 10 m spatial resolution

Sentinel-2 RGB [432] 10m

Sentinel-3 SLSTR 1km

Sentinel-3 SLSTR 10m

Figure 15 Left: Sentinel-2 image acquired over TernaMag mine, Center: Sentinel-3 SLSTR LST image at its native spatial resolution of 1 km, Right: Thermal sharpened Sentinel-3 SLSTR LST data at 10 m spatial resolution

Sentinel-2 RGB [432] 10m

Sentinel-3 SLSTR 1km

Sentinel-3 SLSTR 10m

NoData

Figure 16 Left: Sentinel-2 image acquired over Canteras mine, Center: Sentinel-3 SLSTR LST image at its native spatial resolution of 1 km, Right: Thermal sharpened Sentinel-3 SLSTR LST data at 10 m spatial resolution

5. Multisensory Data Fusion of Sentinel-5P

5.1 Introduction

Monitoring air pollutant concentrations is a vital aspect of responsible and sustainable mining practices. It is essential at mining sites to ensure the health and safety of workers, protect the environment, comply with regulations, optimise operations, manage risks, and maintain positive community relations. However, modelling the spatial distribution of air pollutants is challenging due to the limited number of ground-level air quality monitoring stations in the vicinity of mining areas. Chemical Transport Models (CTMs) serve as valuable computational tools for simulating air pollutant concentrations. By integrating data on emissions, meteorological conditions, and topographical features, these models offer insights across a range of spatial and temporal scales, thereby enhancing our understanding of air quality dynamics. However, the accuracy of these models often relies on the quality and resolution of the input data, as well as the assumptions underlying the chemical and physical processes modelled. On the other hand, spaceborne sensors have transformed the field of air quality monitoring by providing extensive spatial coverage and frequent observations. Spaceborne sensors such as TROPOMI onboard Sentinel-5P have played a vital role in mapping air pollutants to detect and measure atmospheric gases from space. However, this data differs from the ground concentrations measured by monitoring stations. As an alternative, multisensory data fusion incorporates measurements from air quality monitoring stations, spaceborne data, and CTMs, which are based on ML methods, and have been a significant advancement in recent years in comprehensively understanding ground-level air quality concentrations.

This chapter presents the preliminary design of a multisensory data fusion framework for estimating near-surface concentrations of various air pollutants, including NO₂, O₃, and CO. It utilises data from Sentinel-5P and proxy data collected from multiple sources. Following this, a description of the data collected, the ML models employed, and the training strategy implemented will be provided.

5.2 Data Collection

Datasets from Sentinel-5P TROPOMI NO₂, O₃ and CO total vertical column concentration and ERA5 meteorological data (temperature, dew point temperature, wind speed and direction, boundary layer height, total evaporation, total precipitation, surface pressure, and solar radiation) in Europe from 17 July 2022 to 31 December 2024 are considered as the main variables of the inputs in the proposed framework. Additional datasets are employed as the covariates of inputs, such as the NDVI from MODIS and topographic properties computed from Multi-Error-Removed Improved-Terrain (MERIT) DEM to increase the robustness of the trained models. Meanwhile, ground station measurements from European Environment Agency (EEA) are regarded as ground truth values. Table 4 summarises the data and sources used to create the training dataset. A brief introduction of each dataset and its relevant preprocessing is provided in the following subsections.

Data type	Data source
Sentinel-5P Precursor TROPOMI Carbon Monoxide Level 2	https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/
Sentinel-5P Precursor TROPOMI Nitrogen Dioxide Level 2	https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/
Sentinel-5P Precursor TROPOMI Ozone Level 2	https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/
EEA air quality monitoring station measurements	https://eeadmz1-downloads-webapp.azurewebsites.net/
ERA5-Land and ERA5 meteorological data	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu
MERIT DEM	https://hydro.iis.u-tokyo.ac.jp/~yamada/MERIT_DEM/index.html
MODIS/Terra Vegetation Indices Monthly Level 3	https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov

Table 4. Data and data sources used for the creation of the Sentinel-5P training dataset

5.2.1 Sentinel-5P TROPOMI Level 2 Products

The TROPOMI instrument aboard the Sentinel-5P satellite measures top-of-atmosphere radiance, from which Level-2 products of atmospheric trace gases such as NO₂, ozone, methane, formaldehyde, and CO are produced. The TROPOMI instrument has a swath width of 2600 km and passes over the equator at approximately 13:30 local solar time. It provides daily global coverage with a spatial resolution of 7.5 x 3.5 km² until August 6, 2019, after which the spatial resolution improved to 5.5 x 3.5 km². The data are projected using the WGS84 projection and are provided as NetCDF files. Auxiliary data regarding the quality of the measurements are also included. Sentinel-5P Level 2 data (version 2.4 and later) were acquired from July 17, 2022, to December 31, 2024, over Europe to create the training dataset.

5.2.2 ERA5-Land and ERA5 Meteorological Data

ERA5-Land and ERA5 are climate and weather reanalysis data products provided by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). ERA5 is a comprehensive atmospheric reanalysis product that offers detailed global meteorological data. It encompasses various weather variables at different atmospheric levels, including temperature, wind speed, humidity, and precipitation. ERA5 data is available at high temporal resolution (hourly) and spatial resolution (approximately 31 km). The dataset covers a wide time range, from 1950 to the present.

ERA5-Land is a companion product to ERA5, with a specific focus on land and a higher spatial resolution of approximately 9 km. It provides various meteorological variables, including wind speed, temperature, surface net solar radiation, surface pressure, total evaporation, and precipitation. Both ERA5 and ERA5-Land data were retrieved from the Climate Data Store (CDS) of the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) for the period between July 17, 2022, and December 31, 2024.

5.2.3 EEA Air Quality Monitoring Station Measurements

Near-surface concentration measurements of various air pollutants are available as hourly averages per EEA monitoring station. Near-surface measurements of various air pollutants from air quality monitoring stations were obtained from the EEA database. The measurements acquired between July 17, 2022, and December 31, 2024, were retrieved from the EEA's Air Quality Download Service.

5.2.4 MERIT DEM

Topography can impact the transport and trapping of surface pollutants (Shetty et al., 2024). To consider the impact of topography, elevation data obtained from the MERIT Digital Elevation Model (DEM) datasets which is generated at a spatial resolution of 90 m by eliminating major error components from existing DEMs (NASA SRTM3 DEM, JAXA AW3D DEM, Viewfinder Panoramas' DEM) (Yamazaki et al., 2019).

5.2.5 MODIS Terra/Aqua Vegetation Indices Monthly Level 3

This product offers monthly global vegetation indices with high spatial resolution. It is a cloud-free spatial composite derived from the gridded 16-day MOD13C2A2 product, which has a resolution of 1 kilometer. The data is provided as a Level 3 product, projected on a 0.05-degree (approximately 5600 meters) geographic Climate Modelling Grid. The dataset spans the period from July 17, 2022, to December 31, 2024, and was retrieved from the NASA Earthdata Datastore Service using the EarthAccess Python library.

5.3 Data Preprocessing and Harmonisation

The collected dataset contains various input features designed to capture the spatio-temporal variability of near-surface concentrations of air pollutants. These features are incorporated into the XGBoost, which is trained using hourly ground station measurements. The input features include Sentinel-5P NO₂, O₃ and CO total vertical column density measurements, meteorological data, topographic information, and vegetation properties. These datasets are available in various spatial resolutions, projections, and formats. To ensure consistency, these features were harmonised to a common grid with a spatial resolution of 1 x 1 km and in the WGS84 projection. This process facilitates the retrieval of values for each ground station location during the overlap time with Sentinel-5P observations.

For each Sentinel-5P image acquired, low-quality measurements that may have been impacted by various factors, such as cloud cover, surface albedo, the presence of snow and ice, saturation, and geometry, were masked out. This was based on the qa_value included in the Sentinel-5P data. The qa_value is a continuous variable ranging from 0 (indicating no data and high uncertainty) to 1 (indicating low uncertainty). This value summarises the different factors affecting the quality of the measurements. We excluded measurements with a qa_value lower than the thresholds defined in the Copernicus specifications to filter out errors and problematic retrievals. Additionally, to further analyse the TROPOMI data, we resampled and regridded the daily acquisitions of CO, NO₂ and O₃ vertical columns using the bilinear

interpolation method. This was done on a regular grid with a spatial resolution of 1 x 1 km, using the WGS84 projection.

Hourly estimates of meteorological parameters, including 2-meter temperature, total precipitation, 10-meter wind speed, solar radiation, and boundary layer height, were obtained from the ERA5-Land and ERA5 reanalysis datasets provided by the ECMWF. Given that Sentinel-5P provides one to two satellite acquisitions at each location per day, we used only the two consecutive hours of the ERA5 datasets that are closest in time to the satellite overpass for each ground station. Each retrieved meteorological parameter layer was resampled and regridded using the bilinear interpolation method to create a common grid with a resolution of 1 x 1 km², following the WGS84 projection. Finally, the meteorological parameters were linearly interpolated to align with the Sentinel-5P acquisition times, thereby reducing temporal inconsistencies between the meteorological data and the satellite observations.

The measurements from the EEA air quality monitoring stations were filtered to include only those observations that had been validated and verified by the reporting countries. These station measurements are available as hourly averages, while the TROPOMI satellite provides one to two instantaneous measurements per day for a given location. Therefore, we only used the two consecutive hours of ground measurements that were closest in time to the satellite overpass for each ground station. To minimise temporal inconsistencies between the station measurements and the satellite data, these ground measurements were linearly interpolated to align with the Sentinel-5P acquisition time.

Each monthly MODIS NDVI product was resampled and regridded using the bilinear interpolation method to create a uniform grid of 1 x 1 km² with a WGS84 projection. The NDVI data corresponds to the previous month of the retrievals from Sentinel-5P for each ground station location.

The topographic properties remain stable over time. For this reason, the MERIT elevation dataset, projected at a resolution of 1 x 1 km² and in WGS84 projection, was utilised to calculate several topographic variables, including slope and the multiscale topographic position index (TPI), using SAGA GIS. The values for each topographic property were extracted for each ground station location.

The values retrieved from each ground station and the Sentinel-5P overpass corresponding to those ground stations were saved in a CSV file. The data collected from 2022 to 2023 will primarily be used for training and testing the model. The data from 2024 will be evaluated separately to assess the model's sensitivity to the training years when measurements from the EEA air quality monitoring stations become available in September 2025.

5.4 ML Model and Training Strategy

The training datasets are utilised to train XGBoost regression models, which are employed to capture the complex non-linear relationships between input features and near-surface concentrations of NO₂, O₃, and CO measured at ground monitoring stations. XGBoost is an ensemble-based machine learning algorithm that implements a gradient boosting framework.

It constructs an additive model composed of decision trees by iteratively optimising a specified loss function. At each iteration, XGBoost fits a new tree to the residuals (prediction errors) of the previous ensemble, using both first- and second-order derivatives of the loss function to enhance optimization efficiency and accuracy.

To regulate model complexity and mitigate the risk of overfitting, hyperparameter tuning is applied. Optimal hyperparameter configurations are determined through a combination of Bayesian optimisation and grid search cross-validation strategies. The implementation leverages the Python-based xgboost library, specifically its regression module (XGBRegressor).

To address data imbalance and improve model focus on rare target values, a cost-sensitive learning approach is applied. This technique assigns higher training costs to underrepresented instances, guiding the model to prioritise them during learning. Specifically, the DenseWeight method (Steininger et al., 2021) calculates instance weights based on the rarity of their target values, estimated using Kernel Density Estimation (KDE). Lower-density (rarer) targets receive higher weights, which are integrated into the training process to enhance prediction accuracy for these critical cases.

5.5 Air Quality Monitoring Service

The service will utilise multisensory data fusion models to estimate the spatial distribution of surface air pollutant concentrations at a spatial resolution of 1 km. Sentinel-5P data retrieved from the CDSE will be fused with proxy data, such as meteorological and topographic data, and the higher-resolution ground-level concentration will be estimated by training ML models with in-situ surface measurements. The downscaled estimations of near-surface concentrations of air pollutants from Sentinel-5P data will be available as GeoTIFF images and stored on the TerraFusion Platform (Figure 17). At the stage of the project, these products will be available upon request. A snapshot of downscaled Sentinel-5P NO₂ acquired over western Europe is illustrated in Figure 18.

Figure 17 Functional view of the TERRAVISION Sentinel-5P Multisensory Data Fusion Service

Figure 18 Downscaled near surface NO₂ concentrations (mg/m³) at 1 km

6. Conclusions

The report describes the initial design of the SR architecture models for enhancing EO data, particularly for mining applications. Four different SR tools have been developed to enhance the spatial resolution of spaceborne data, particularly for applications in mining-related services. The first tool focuses on pansharpener PRISMA hyperspectral images to improve their spatial resolution from 30 meters to 5 meters. This enhancement is achieved by integrating the high spatial resolution PAN band, which is acquired simultaneously and included in the PRISMA datasets. The second tool employs a DL-based SR model to enhance the spatial resolution of Sentinel-2's coarse bands, bringing them up to the resolution of its finer bands (10 meters). The third tool focuses on sharpening thermal data from Sentinel-3's SLSTR by fusing it with higher spatial resolution multispectral data from Sentinel-2. The fourth tool downscales data from Sentinel-5P to estimate near-surface concentrations of air pollutants at a higher resolution of 1 km. This is accomplished by combining the Sentinel-5P data with additional information, including meteorological data and land cover maps. This document describes the initial design and development of the four individual SR components. A detailed description of each component is provided to facilitate the interpretation of the design.

The code for the SR tools is available on GitHub at the following repository: <https://github.com/mariadek/TERRAVISION-Project>

Several constraints and weaknesses were identified during the development and testing of the four super-resolution components. We will address these issues to finalise the design of the proposed super-resolution architectures. The planned next steps are as follows:

- Develop a memory-efficient version of the GSA pansharpener approach.
- Develop a DL-based SR model to enhance the spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 beyond 10 m.

Bibliography

- Alicandro, M., Candigliota, E., Dominici, D., Immordino, F., Masin, F., Pascucci, N., Quaresima, R., & Zollini, S. (2022). Hyperspectral PRISMA and Sentinel-2 Preliminary Assessment Comparison in Alba Fucens and Sinuessa Archaeological Sites (Italy). *Land*, 11(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11112070>
- Gal, Y., & Ghahramani, Z. (2015). Dropout as a Bayesian Approximation: Representing Model Uncertainty in Deep Learning. *33rd International Conference on Machine Learning, ICML 2016*, 3, 1651–1660. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1506.02142v6>
- Gao, F., Masek, J., Schwaller, M., & Hall, F. (2006). On the blending of the landsat and MODIS surface reflectance: Predicting daily landsat surface reflectance. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 44(8), 2207–2218. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2006.872081>
- Lanaras, C., Bioucas-Dias, J., Galliani, S., Baltsavias, E., & Schindler, K. (2018). Super-resolution of Sentinel-2 images: Learning a globally applicable deep neural network. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 146, 305–319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2018.09.018>
- Maurer, T. (2013). *HOW TO PAN-SHARPEN IMAGES USING THE GRAM-SCHMIDT PAN-SHARPEN METHOD-A RECIPE*.
- Michel, J., Vinasco-Salinas, J., Inglada, J., & Hagolle, O. (2022). SEN2VEN μ S, a Dataset for the Training of Sentinel-2 Super-Resolution Algorithms. *Data 2022*, Vol. 7, Page 96, 7(7), 96. <https://doi.org/10.3390/DATA7070096>
- Scheffler, D., Hollstein, A., Diedrich, H., Segl, K., & Hostert, P. (2017). AROSICS: An Automated and Robust Open-Source Image Co-Registration Software for Multi-Sensor Satellite Data. *Remote Sensing 2017*, Vol. 9, Page 676, 9(7), 676. <https://doi.org/10.3390/RS9070676>
- Shetty, S., Schneider, P., Stebel, K., David Hamer, P., Kylling, A., & Koren Berntsen, T. (2024). Estimating surface NO₂ concentrations over Europe using Sentinel-5P TROPOMI observations and Machine Learning. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2024.114321>
- Steininger, M., Kobs, K., Davidson, P., Krause, A., & Hotho, A. (2021). Density-based weighting for imbalanced regression. *Machine Learning*, 110(8), 2187–2211. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10994-021-06023-5>
- Yamazaki, D., Ikeshima, D., Sosa, J., Bates, P. D., Allen, G. H., & Pavelsky, T. M. (2019). MERIT Hydro: A High-Resolution Global Hydrography Map Based on Latest Topography Dataset. *Water Resources Research*, 55(6), 5053–5073. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019WR024873>

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